
Paper 12

PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS AMONG SPOUSES OF MALE AT RISK DRINKERS-A STUDY

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Abstract:

The consequences of alcoholism on the mental health of spouses of lifetime at risk drinkers are only known from the studies on alcoholics. The effects of alcoholism on a relationship or marriage are huge strain on the relationship. A study was conducted in a community of Mangalore. The researcher have been used interview schedule for collecting information on the objective of understanding personal profile, causes and problems .These spouses were less likely to be homemakers. Women often suffer cruel physical and emotional abuse from their alcoholic husbands. Even when he is not overtly abusive he's often disgusting in the way he talks and behaves when he's drunk. The spouses of alcoholics are usually so relieved when treatment is successful that they often think their marital troubles are over. Its true addiction makes it impossible to resolve marital conflicts. Descriptive research design has been used for the study by taking 50 samples. The study found that 60 per cent of the female spouses of alcoholics have been adjusted and also they try to keep themselves busy, socio economic conditions of them are poor.

Keywords: Alcoholism, Addiction, Relationship, Abuse, Stress, Treatment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The problem of alcoholism until a few decades ago was considered a moral; problem and a sign of social irresponsibility[1]. Alcoholism is one among the major social problem that our nation faces and it is a major block to the development of rural as well as urban areas. It is harmful not only for the individual but also for his family and the society at large. The emotional response to addictive illness in family members... frequently have their roots in guilt feelings. Grief is an emotional responds of his wife to addiction. For family members, grief is the result of all sorts of losses. Loss of prestige, loss of family and personal dignity, loss of feeling of love, loss of care and understanding, loss of security, loss of friends, loss of finance, loss of each and every areas of their life. According to Keller and Efron(1955), Alcoholism is characterized by the repeated drinking of alcoholic beverages to an extent that exceeds customary use or compliance with the social customs of the community and that adversely affects the drinkers health or interferes with his social or economic functioning. Addiction is the problem which affects not only the individual but the family and society also.

2. ALCOHOL AS A CAUSE OF FAMILY PROBLEM

It has always been known that problematic drinkers cause problems not only to themselves but also to their spouse, children, parents and their family members [8]. The impact of problematic drinking on the family is especially on the adolescents.

(i) **Roles:** Problematic drinking can change the roles played by family members in relation to one another and the outside world, the drinker might cease to perform his previous functions as a breadwinner or in relation to the support and supervision of children household chores or recreational activities [2].

(ii) **Routines:** The addicts behavior is likely to become unpredictable and disruptive imparting the family's capacity to plan activities in advance or to stick to familiar routines

(iii) **Rituals:** Family gathering such as Christmas or birthday, designed to celebrate and integrate the family, may be particularly subject to disruption either because of the absence of the drinker or perhaps much worsen their presence [8]

(iv) **Finance:** Money spent on alcohol is not available for other purpose. An alcohol problem may impair or destroy the drinker's capacity to earn a livelihood. Reducing earnings or unemployment are not infrequent consequences of drinking problem and these naturally affect the other members of the family and can have all sorts of repercussions [5]

3. IMPACT OF THE ALCOHOLISM IN THE FAMILY

(i) **Social Impact :** Interpersonal relationships are poor with neighbors and relatives due to the alcohol dependents behavior. They would be constant fights and arguments in the family and neighborhood [4]

(ii) **Financial Impact :** Absenteeism or ill health leading to lose of income[5]. Loans debts from various people.

(iii) **Values & Moral Standards:** Values in the family are very poor. Lying, stealing and fights are common [4]

(iv) **Cultural Areas:** Festivals, customs, rituals, tradition are all forgotten. Spouse may not have money or interest or due to ill health, may not be able to celebrate a festival.

(v) **Spouse or Partner Stress:** Alcoholism has a transforming effect on the spouse or partner that can create significant mental trauma and physical health problems. Divorce rates among couples where one or both partner's drinks are much higher than average [3]. As alcohol abuse or addiction progresses, the non-drinking spouse often grows into a compulsive care-taking role, which creates feelings of resentment, self-pity and exhaustion [4]

(vi) **Marital Sufferings:** Poor spousal communication [6], Increased anger and distress [6], Reduced intimacy and sexual desire, Increased marital abuse, Depleting finances spent on alcohol, The relationship between an alcohol abuser and his or her family is complex [7]. 'Family members report experiencing guilt, shame, anger, fear, grief and isolation due to the presence of an alcohol abuser in the family [10]. They are often subjected when they confront the drinking behavior of their alcohol abusing family members. Spouses in families where there is chronic excessive use of alcohol are frequently separated.

(vii) **Effects of Alcoholism on Families:** Treating alcoholic families is difficult and complex. Often treatment is not entirely successful for family members, even when the alcohol abuse or addict eventually reforms [9]. The effects of alcoholism in families are difficult to overcome; yet

without treatment, they can be devastating for the long-term. With the right approach and support, positive steps can be taken to improve lives [7]. Healthcare professionals may recommend a multi-faceted treatment approach that includes group family therapy, as well as individualized treatment for each family member [8] .

4. TREATMENT METHODS

The treatment may take the form of one or more of the following pedagogies. The intervention based on the result of this study indicates that greater psychological distress among these wives was most strongly associated with lower satisfaction with the marital relationship, presence of domestic violence, lower perceived social support from family [5]. The key treatment methods include Out-Patient Programs, In-Patient Programs, Peer Support Groups, Psycho-Social Therapy and Medication-Assisted Treatment.

5. CONCLUSION

By concluding it can be said that alcoholism is a family disease and the spouse of an alcoholic is the most affected person in the family. Alcohol is a weakness of character. The moralist looks at it as a vice, law finds the consequential act of alcoholism as a crime, the clergyman considers it as a sin, a psychiatric professional recognizes it as a disease, which can be treated. It is not only harmful to the individual but also families. If timely help is not provided to such families, they may become a problem to the society.

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